

THE CYANINE DYES OF THE PYRIDINE SERIES.

By M. Q. DOJA.

p-Dimethylaminobenzaldehyde and *p*-nitrosodimethylaniline have been condensed with the methochloride, methobromide, and methoiodide of 2-methylpyridine, and the properties of the products examined including their absorption spectra and fluorescence.

The cyanine dyes (for a general survey see 'The Cyanine Dyes' by M. Q. Doja, *Chem. Rev.*, 1932, 11, 273) contain in their molecules the characteristic arrangement, one equivalent of an acid radicle and two nitrogen atoms of basic function joined together by a chain of conjugated double bonds.

(I)

In view of the great sensitising power of (I, X=I), synthesised by Mills and Pope (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 946), it was thought of interest to investigate the influence of change of anions on the properties of the compound, and it was with this object in view that the present work was undertaken.

In the first place, the three halides (chloride, bromide and iodide) were chosen for comparison. The chloride corresponding to (I) has been obtained by the condensation of α -picoline methochloride, prepared by a modification of the method of Ramsay (*Phil. Mag.*, 1917, 2, v, 277) with *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde in presence of piperidine and the corresponding bromide from α -picoline methobromide. These new dyes resemble each other closely and exhibit the general characteristic of cyanine dyes. In concentrated aqueous solution all the three substances give rise to orange coloured solutions and brownish yellow solutions in dilute condition. The reddish tinge of concentrated solutions is most predominant in the chloride and least so in the iodide. They dye cotton an orange colour

with a reddish tinge, the variation being the same as in their aqueous solutions. On exposure to sunlight, the dyed cloth begins to fade after three days. All the three compounds give similar absorption spectra showing a band of selective absorption in the blue with a maximum at about λ 4800.

The so-called *p*-dimethylaminoanils of heterocyclic ammonium compounds (Smith, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 2288; Bloch and Hamer, *Phot. J.*, 1930, 70, 374) are desensitisers for the photographic plate (Hamer, *Phot. J.*, 1929, 69, 409) in contrast to the styryl compounds which are sensitisers.

p-Dimethylaminoanil of 2-methylpyridine methoiodide was first prepared by Kaufmann and Valette (*Ber.*, 1912, 45, 1736); the related chloride and bromide have now been obtained. They are highly coloured like the styryl compounds, and their colour in solution is discharged by mineral acids and restored by alkalis. The three compounds have similar absorption spectra, showing a band of selective absorption in the green with maxima at about λ 5100.

The fluorescence of all the six compounds is shown in Table I.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Absorption spectra were taken in the visible region only with dilute solutions of the compounds in absolute methyl alcohol. The solutions of the styryl compounds were 2×10^{-5} *M* and those of the anil compounds were 1×10^{-5} *M*.

The fluorescence was observed with solutions of same strength as employed for taking the absorption spectra, with the help of a thousand candle power point-o-lite lamp as a light source, a lens and condenser and Wallace colour filters. Dyeing was performed with tannic acid mordanted cloth.

2-p-Dimethylaminostyrylpyridine Methochloride.—A mixture of 2-methylpyridine methochloride (2.5 g., dry) and *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde (3 g.) in absolute methyl alcohol (45 c.c.) and piperidine (20 drops) was boiled for 9 hours on a sand-bath. After cooling the dark red liquid was left in a vacuum desiccator for 48 hours. The sticky solid, thus obtained, was placed on a porous plate and left in a desiccator for a week. On recrystallisation from methyl alcohol it was obtained as deep red crystals, m.p. 117°, yield 1.8 g. (Found: Cl, 12.6. $C_{16}H_{19}N_2Cl$ requires Cl, 12.9 per cent).

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TABLE I.

Colour of the fluorescent beam.

Wallace colour filter No.	Styryl chloride.	Styryl bromide.	Styryl iodide.	Anil chloride.	Anil bromide.	Anil iodide.
1	Very weak red	Weak red	Weak red	Nil	Nil	Nil
2	Very weak red	Red	Red	Weak red	Weak red	Nil
3	Light greenish yellow	Weak orange red	Orange	Pink	Weak red	Very weak pink
4	Very faint pink	Weak orange red	Yellowish red	Yellowish pink	Orange red	Nil
5	Dull yellow	Greenish yellow	Greenish yellow	Greenish yellow	Greenish yellow	Very weak greenish yellow
6	Dull yellow	Greenish yellow	Greenish yellow	Greenish yellow	Greenish yellow	Very weak greenish yellow
7	Dull yellow with an orange tinge.	Green	Dull yellow	Greenish yellow	Green	Nil
8	Dull yellow with an orange tinge.	Weak green	Dull yellow	Bluish green	Bluish green	Nil
9	Yellow	Weak yellow (towards the light, but no trace on the side away from the source).	Brownish yellow (appearing towards the source and disappearing towards the side away from the source).	Very weak green.	Nil	Nil
10	Yellow (the end away from the source becoming weaker).	Yellow	Yellow	Yellowish green	Yellowish green	Very weak yellow

Similarly *2-p-Dimethylaminostyrylpyridine Methobromide* was prepared from 2-methylpyridine methobromide (2 g.) and *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde (2 g.) in absolute methyl alcohol (40 c.c.) with piperidine (0.4 c.c.) by heating for 6 hours. The red liquid was placed in a desiccator for 3 days and the separated solids recrystallised from methyl alcohol in vermilion red silky needles, m.p. 262°, yield 1.6 g. (Found : Br, 24.9. $C_{16}H_{16}N_2Br$ requires Br, 25.1 per cent).

p-Dimethylaminoanil of 2-methylpyridine methochloride was prepared from 2-methylpyridine methochloride (2.5 g.) and *p*-nitrosodimethylaniline (2.5 g.) in absolute alcohol (25 c.c.) with piperidine (20 drops) by heating for 9 hours. The crystalline precipitate was recrystallised from methyl alcohol, giving brownish black lustrous needles, m.p. 235°, yield 0.8 g. (Found : Cl, 13.2. $C_{13}H_{18}N_2Cl$ requires Cl, 12.9 per cent).

p-Dimethylaminoanil of 2-methylpyridine methobromide was prepared from 2-methylpyridine methobromide (1.9 g.) and *p*-nitrosodimethylaniline (1.5 g.) in alcoholic solution with piperidine by heating for 8 hours. The solution was kept in a desiccator and the separated solids recrystallised from methyl alcohol in shining blue black needles, m.p. 237°, yield 0.6 g. (Found : Br, 25.3. $C_{15}H_{18}N_2$ Br requires Br, 25.0 per cent).

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